

Illegal patents: The study of unfair practices in patents involving video games

The study of unfair and deceptive practices in patents involving video games

Sundarapariurnan Narayanan,

University of Bordeaux, AI Tech Ethics, sundar.narayanan@aitechethics.com

Sandeep Vishwakarma,

Researcher, AI Tech Ethics, sandeep.vishwakarma@aitechethics.com

The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) Act prohibits unfair and deceptive practices in commerce, including video games. The FTC distinguishes between deceptive practices, which mislead or are likely to mislead consumers, and unfair practices, which cause substantial injury that cannot be reasonably avoided. In the context of video games, deceptive practices include misleading advertising, loot boxes, microtransactions, UI misdirection, and emotional manipulation. Unfair practices include predatory monetization, grinding mechanics, time-limited events, social pressure, and inaccessible content. Manipulative matchmaking, pay-to-win mechanics, exploitative monetization, and time-gating content in video games can all potentially violate FTC requirements. Many of these systems and methods feature in leading video games and many such video game organizations have patents on these systems and methods leveraging Artificial intelligence or machine learning. While there is an underlying understanding that technology that is illegal cannot be patented, there are very few instances where such patents have been contested. In the emerging world of multi-model engagement, this research examines 85 patents relating to video games to identify the unfair practices that are part of these patents. This research aims to exhibit the need for research at the intersection of Patent and Ethics, as previously seen in Biotechnology.

CCS CONCEPTS • **Social and professional topics** • Computing / technology policy • Intellectual property • Patents

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Dark Patterns; Unfair design, Video Games

1 Introduction

The U.S. Federal Trade Commission Act (FTC Act) prohibits "unfair or deceptive acts or practices" in commerce, a prohibition that extends to banks and is enforced by the FDIC and Federal Reserve. Unfairness requires substantial consumer injury that is not reasonably avoidable and not outweighed by benefits, while deception involves material misrepresentations that mislead consumers. The FTC enforces **Section 5** of the FTC Act in consumer transactions, focusing on practices that cause substantial injury to consumers, which is not reasonably

avoidable. This regulatory approach extends to vulnerable consumers, such as children or low-income individuals, who may require additional protection. Definitions of deceptive and unfair practices as per [1] are as follows:

Unfair practices	Deceptive practices
<p>An act or practice is unfair where it</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Causes or is likely to cause substantial injury to consumers, • Cannot be reasonably avoided by consumers, and • Is not outweighed by countervailing benefits to consumers or to competition. 	<p>An act or practice is deceptive where</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A representation, omission, or practice misleads or is likely to mislead the consumer • A consumer's interpretation of the representation, omission, or practice is considered reasonable under the circumstances; and • The misleading representation, omission, or practice is material.

1.1 Unfair practices enforcements in recently

While both unfair and deceptive practices pose challenges in games, unfair practices tend to be more discernible. Deceptive practices often hinge on misrepresentations or false claims, which can be subtle and difficult to discern without thorough investigation. In contrast, unfair practices frequently involve blatant or inequitable treatment of players, making them more apparent. This paper deals with unfair practices. Recent enforcements involving Genshin Impact and Epic Games indicates stronger enforcement direction from the FTC.

For instance, in January 2025, in the case of Genshin Impact (developed by HoYoverse), the FTC alleged that HoYoverse violated COPPA by collecting children's personal data without parental consent and deceived consumers about the costs and odds of winning rare in-game prizes. The case was settled with USD 20 mn in fines and required HoYoverse to obtain parental consent for purchases by children under 16, disclose loot box odds and prices, and comply with COPPA [2].

Similarly, in December 2024, in the case of Epic Games' Fortnite, the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) initiated a refund program, totaling over \$72 million, for consumers deceived into making unwanted purchases, based on the settlement announced in December 2022. The case involved allegations that Epic Games employed "dark patterns" to induce purchases, permitted children to incur unauthorized charges, and restricted access to content for users disputing charges [3].

1.2 Unfair design in video games

Video and online games have increasingly incorporated various unfair and deceptive design practices, raising concerns about consumer protection and player well-being. Many games now employ deceptive monetization techniques that exploit cognitive biases and vulnerabilities. For instance, some games use predatory monetization, default to purchase options, and use UI misdirection to drive spending [4]. Loot boxes and other microtransaction systems have been compared to electronic gambling machines, potentially leading to overspending, especially among vulnerable populations like adolescents [5]. Some in-game purchasing systems capitalize on informational advantages and data manipulation to optimize offers and incentivize continuous spending while offering limited consumer protections [5].

1.3 Unfair design in patents

Interestingly, deception is not limited to monetization but extends to game design itself. Researchers have created games specifically designed to exploit cognitive biases, leading players away from optimal strategies [6]. Many of the games have patents for their technology and game mechanics, including influencing purchase decisions or microtransactions and manipulative matchmaking with other players or non-player objects. The

patent system is designed to protect inventions that are novel and useful. One of the underlying criteria for the patent is that the underlying invention must fall within the realm of lawful activities. Given the proliferation of the patents in the gaming industry, the possibility of applied or published patents having contents that are unfair and deceptive as described above cannot be ruled out. However, based on our review, we have not come across any research that examines the above research question, "Can patents contain unfair and deceptive practices that may be potentially illegal under the FTC Act [Section 5](#)?"

1.4 Types of unfair patterns

We compiled a list of 15 unfair patterns in video games based on [[6](#), [7](#), [8](#), [9](#), [10](#), [11](#), [12](#), [13](#), [14](#), [19](#)]. They are as follows:

- Event lockouts: Event lockouts in video games, offer exclusive rewards for limited-time participation, creating a sense of urgency and exclusivity, potentially increasing player engagement and retention.
- Daily Quest Limits: Restricts daily tasks players can complete. After reaching the limit, they must wait for a reset or buy more. Research has demonstrated that poor balancing can contribute to poor engagement in games, highlighting the need for careful consideration when implementing such mechanics.
- Timers for building/upgrading mean players wait for actions to be complete or can pay to speed up the process.
- Energy Recharge System: Players have limited energy that depletes during activities, requiring time or payment to recharge.
- Loot Box Manipulation: Designing loot boxes with low drop rates to exploit players' desires, driving repeated purchases for rare items.
- Forced Advertisements: Mandatory ads players must watch for features/rewards, often leading to purchases for ad removal.
- Excessive Grind Walls: High requirements in games that make progress tedious and time-consuming without purchases.
- Energy/Stamina Systems: Players have limited energy to play; once depleted, they must wait to recharge or buy more.
- Expedited Progression: Players can buy in-game currency or boosts to level up faster and access rewards sooner than non-paying players.
- Enhanced Equipment: Paid options for superior gear that boost player stats, creating an unfair advantage over non-paying players.
- Unlockable Characters: Premium heroes accessible via paid transactions, offering unique abilities that non-paying players lack.
- Exclusive Power-Ups: Unique in-game abilities available only through real-money purchases, making paying players have an edge.
- Teaming with influencers means pairing novice players with popular streamers to showcase advanced gameplay and exclusive items.
- Limited Pool Pairing matches players without recent purchases against those with powerful items, creating gameplay disparities.
- Skill Discrepancy Pairing: Novice players matched with skilled ones, causing frustration and pressure to buy upgrades

The objective of the research is to identify indicators of unfair practices embedded in video or online game patents.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data gathering and analysis

To identify and analyze unfair practices in gaming, we implemented a systematic, multi-step approach. Firstly, a patent search and filtering process was conducted. Using Google Patents, we employed keywords such as "influencing purchases," "matchmaking," and "microtransactions" to locate patents published after January 1, 2014, within the United States. This search yielded 858 patents, which were subsequently narrowed down to 85 relevant patents based on a review of their abstracts. These patents were analyzed against a framework of 15 types of unfair and deceptive designs, aligned with the Federal Trade Commission's (FTC) expectations. The contents of the 85 identified patents were further analyzed using two large language models (e.g., OpenAI GPT-4o-mini and Gemini 1.5 flash). This analysis aimed to identify patterns indicative of unfair and deceptive practices within the 15 predefined categories for every paragraph in the identified 85 patents. We adopted a two-model approach to avoid possible failure to retrieve relevant content by any individual model. Subsequently, there was a phase of manual review and validation of the findings from the models. The manual review included the elimination of false positives and the validation of possible deceptive designs by verifying them against the original patents (patent page and claims mentioned in it) to ensure accuracy. Finally, findings were summarized, highlighting key results and their implications for regulatory and industry practices.

2.2 About the dataset

Patent documentation employs alphanumeric kind codes to signify the type and publication stage of patent records. Commonly used codes in the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) denote a patent application publication (pre-grant publication) as A1, a patent issued from an application without prior pre-grant publication as B1, and a patent issued from an application that was previously published as a pre-grant publication as B2 [15]. The patents identified for review had 60 A1, 5 B1, and 20 B2 overall.

The patents primarily related to various systems, methods, and platforms for enhancing multiplayer video game experiences, driving microtransactions, and improving matchmaking. They also cover aspects such as personalized messaging, live interventions, and integrating real-world content into gaming. Additionally, some patents focus on efficient resource management for streaming content and using biometric data for social interactive applications. The assignees with most number of patents as part of the identified 85 patents were as follows:

Assignee	No of patents
Activision Publishing, Inc.	11
Electronic Arts Inc.	6
Sean Malek	5
Sony Interactive Entertainment LLC	4
Sony Interactive Entertainment Inc.	3
Vetnos Llc	3
Nvidia Corporation	2
South Park Digital Studios LLC	2
Rovi Guides, Inc.	2
Double Shot LLC	2

3 Results

3.1 Findings

We took the detailed patent description from each of the 85 URLs (gathered from the search results) we found and used OpenAI GPT-4-o-mini and Gemini 1.5 flash to run parallel search agents that look at the 15 unfair practices listed above on every page (about 500 words is considered as one page) of the patent description. The models identified 302 pages—some of them instances discovered by both models—as pages with unfair patterns from 52 patents.

We manually reviewed the 302 instances to validate if the unfair patterns were identified by leveraging the language models. Many of the 302 instances were identified to have more than one unfair pattern, thereby making the number of pages with unique unfair patterns 595. We eliminated 92% of the 595 instances as false positives (i.e., instances that the language models were misclassified and instances that were duplicates of earlier findings). The reasons for false positives include, (a) the language models hallucinate in identifying the unfair pattern, (b) the issue identified were part of the context explaining the state of affairs of the domain in the patent and not the invention itself, and (c) the language models provided varied results: OpenAI provided 155 results and Gemini provided 437 results, many of which were duplicates, thereby requiring elimination.

The rest of the instances were reviewed to validate unfair patterns. We observed 34 unique instances of unfair patterns from 10 patents (3 B2 and 7 A1 patents). These unfair patterns were determined based on 3 primary conditions: (a) causes or is likely to cause substantial injury to consumers, (b) cannot be reasonably avoided by consumers, and (c) is not outweighed by countervailing benefits to consumers or to competition. Illustrative instances of the unfair patterns identified are listed in [Table 1](#) below.

Table 1: Illustrative instances of unfair patterns identified

Type	Illustration (excerpts from patent text)	Analysis
Excessive grind walls	A voting requirement, requiring that the user complete an action for his or her vote or supervote to count. A supervote can also, optionally, negate any timing requirements between votes. For example, following a normal vote, a user may be prevented from voting again for some period of time. However, a supervote may allow the user to resume voting immediately. Alternatively, or in addition, a voting requirement, as shown in the third row of FIG. 28, may appear, requiring that the user complete an action for his or her vote or supervote to count. Such behaviors/actions as may be required for supervoting can help to create more accurate user profiles, as well as accomplish marketing objectives relevant to a sponsor's marketing objectives. Examples of actions include requiring the user to click to be redirected to another page on the platform, to provide information to upgrade an account and/or by providing user verification information, such as a phone number, click a sponsor-chosen Facebook fanpage to "Like" the page, click a sponsor-chosen URL, opt-in to sharing personal data with the sponsor, be introduced to an e-commerce purchase opportunity, follow the sponsor on platform to generate a larger social-influence, watch a sponsor-chosen advertisement and answer questions about user-reaction to the advertisement, install an app (e.g., a sponsor app available at Google Play® or the Apple® store), download a song from the platform or a music-network, confirm user characteristics, such as age, physical	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Requirements create tedious gameplay, discouraging casual players from progressing.- Users must complete actions to vote, mirroring grind mechanics in games.- Supervotes allow immediate voting, but require user engagement, increasing grind-like behavior.- Actions for voting can exploit user time, similar to excessive grind walls.

Type	Illustration (excerpts from patent text)	Analysis
Enhanced equipment	<p>location, interests, and/or date of birth, and/or require the user to upload a video of his or herself for verification.</p> <p>"In an operation 812, responsive to a determination that the first player purchased the in-game item, the player profile may be updated to reflect the purchase and the first player may be matched (e.g., match variables and/or coefficients tuned) to play a second gameplay session in which the in-game item is suitable to be used."</p> <p>"For example, if the in-game item is a weapon (e.g., an accurate and powerful sniper rifle), the second gameplay session may be selected because the weapon is highly effective in the second gameplay session. Doing so may encourage the first player to make subsequent purchases due to the satisfaction of effectively using the in-game item during the second gameplay session."</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paid gear creates a disparity between paying and non-paying players. - Enhanced equipment leads to unequal gameplay experiences and outcomes. - Players with superior gear gain significant advantages in competitive scenarios. - This system incentivizes further purchases, perpetuating the unfair advantage.
Event lockout	<p>"During the opt-in period, players of other electronic gaming machines may receive, for example, notice of the upcoming secondary game, the designated award for winning the secondary game, an option to participate in the secondary game, and a countdown timer showing the time remaining for joining the secondary game. When the countdown is finished and the opt-in period has ended, the secondary game creation and management system may prevent any further players from joining the secondary game and move on to the next step to enable secondary gameplay for the validated players."</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited-time participation creates urgency, pressuring players to act quickly. - Missed opportunities lead to potential financial penalties for late access. - Exclusive rewards incentivize participation, creating a sense of unfair advantage. - Countdown timers emphasize scarcity, manipulating player behavior and decision-making.
Exclusive Powerups	<p>Powerups may be available to users to affect play in the secondary game. They may be awarded based on online activities, such as social gaming activities, or based on activities on premises, such as underlying electronic gaming machine play or any other reward mechanisms. Powerups may be awarded individually or in groups and may also be gifted from one users to one or more other users. In some embodiments, powerups available to the player may comprise powerups relating to the secondary game which may affect secondary gameplay for one or more players of the secondary game. Powerups may also include a power up to generate a score multiplier for the secondary game for one or more players, which may increase or decrease their scoring, position, and/or progression. The score multiplier may be limited to certain amount of time, certain amount of plays, or random amounts of time or plays in the underlying game. In some embodiments, powerups may include a powerup to enable one or more players of the secondary game to share scoring or wins amongst themselves. The sharing may be limited to a certain amount of time, certain amount of plays, or random amounts of time or plays in the underlying game.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exclusive power-ups create a pay-to-win environment for players. - Paying players gain significant advantages over non-paying players. - Unique abilities disrupt fair competition among all players. - Real-money purchases lead to unequal gameplay experiences.
Expedited progression	<p>"In FIG. 9B, the durational information platform provides a duration to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Players can pay to significantly reduce gameplay duration, creating an unfair

Type	Illustration (excerpts from patent text)	Analysis
Limited Pool pairing	<p>completion of 45 minutes to the player. In addition, the durational information platform provides an option for the player to reduce the duration to completion to 25 minutes if the player chooses to use (e.g., purchase) resource X. In this manner, the player is provided with concrete durational information as to whether or not to select resource X."</p> <p>In an implementation, when a player makes a game-related purchase, microtransaction engine 128 may encourage future purchases by matching the player (e.g., using matchmaking described herein) in a gameplay session that will utilize the game-related purchase. Doing so may enhance a level of enjoyment by the player for the game-related purchase, which may encourage future purchases. For example, if the player purchased a particular weapon, microtransaction engine 128 may match the player in a gameplay session in which the particular weapon is highly effective, giving the player an impression that the particular weapon was a good purchase. This may encourage the player to make future purchases to achieve similar gameplay results.</p>	<p>advantage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-paying players face longer wait times, hindering their progression and enjoyment. - The option to buy boosts promotes a pay-to-win dynamic in the game. - This system incentivizes spending over skill or time investment, leading to inequality. <p>- Limited Pool Pairing creates unfair advantages for players with purchases.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Players without purchases face significant gameplay disadvantages. - Matchmaking favors those who spend money, leading to disparities. - Encourages spending by showcasing purchased items' effectiveness in matches.
Loot box manipulation	<p>"If the player deposits, for example, \$100.00 into the machine, he would be given \$100 credit at the machine. He could then begin to play and either start to win or lose. If the player's credit begins to diminish, then at every predetermined increment (in this example \$20), he would be given a chance to win his money back, back to 100 dollars (or more than 100 dollars, in one embodiment) in the form of a 'bonus round' and so on. That is, for every 20 dollar losing to the machine, or for every 20 dollar subtraction from the original value, e.g. at \$80, 60, 40 levels or thresholds, and so on, this opportunity comes up (and has a specific probability of winning and amount of winning corresponding to that)."</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low drop rates create a sense of scarcity and urgency for players. - Players are incentivized to spend more to chase rare items. - Bonus rounds exploit emotional responses to losses, encouraging further spending. - The design manipulates player psychology, leading to repeated purchases.
Skill discrepancy pairing	<p>In the context of a junior player aspiring to become an expert sniper, the microtransaction engine may match this player with a highly skilled sniper. This pairing is designed to encourage the junior player to make game-related purchases, such as a sniper rifle or other items used by the marquee player. For instance, if the junior player purchases a specific weapon, the microtransaction engine may ensure that they are matched in a gameplay session where that weapon is particularly effective. This creates a positive reinforcement loop, where the player feels that their purchase was worthwhile, thus incentivizing future purchases.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -System prioritizes performance, potentially mismatching novices with skilled players. - Junior players face skilled opponents, leading to frustration and imbalance. - Encourages microtransactions by matching players with effective purchased items.

Type	Illustration (excerpts from patent text)	Analysis
	Additionally, the system may suggest optimal group compositions for players looking to form or join teams. By analyzing player profiles, including explicit preferences, past purchases, and performance metrics, the system can identify groups that have historically performed well or provided high enjoyment levels. This matchmaking process not only enhances the gameplay experience but also subtly encourages players to engage in purchases that align with their desired playstyle.	- Suggests optimal teams, reinforcing the need for purchases to compete.

3.2 Discussion

3.2.1 User exploitation with unfair patterns

A study of 1104 players identified 35 separate techniques across eight domains, including game dynamics designed to drive spending, pay-to-win mechanics, and the general presence of microtransactions [18]. These practices often do not align with existing consumer protection regulations, raising concerns about their ethical implications. While previous research has exhibited the presence of temporal, monetary, and psychological dark patterns, including aesthetic manipulations, paywalls, and periodic rewards resembling gambling elements, [13] this analysis revealed the existence of such patterns in patents.

The analysis reveals several indicators of unfair patterns that (a) create competitive imbalance, (b) exploit players' 'fear of missing out,' (c) exploit players with incentives for losses incurred, and (d) influence purchases or microtransactions. For instance, "paid gear" creates significant competitive imbalances. Players with limited budgets are at a distinct disadvantage, facing reduced gameplay enjoyment and a diminished sense of fairness. This system inherently favors those who can afford to spend, creating an unequal and potentially frustrating playing field where consumer choice is limited. Similarly, limited-time events and exclusive power-ups create a sense of urgency and a pay-to-win dynamic, respectively. These features incentivize spending over skill and time investment. Further, "scarcity and urgency" tactics exploit the players' 'fear of missing out,' such as low drop rates and limited-time events, creating a sense of urgency, manipulating players into making impulsive purchases. Similarly, "Losses and incentives" exploits by offering small incentives after losses, influencing a cycle of continued play, masking the negative financial impact

Matchmaking systems can be designed to favor players with purchases, creating an uneven playing field. Additionally, the influence of streamers and the pressure to emulate their success can drive impulsive spending on in-game items. This creates a social dynamic where players feel pressured to spend money to keep up with others and maintain a competitive edge. "Exploiting player desires" further exacerbates this issue. By leveraging the allure of rare items and the illusion of improved odds, developers encourage repeated spending, often masking the true odds of success.

Many of the above are not actions that are in the best interest of the players. They have dark design monetization as a primary goal [17] and highlight that the dark patterns in video games to be unethical and that such patterns manipulate players against their best interest [20].

3.2.2 Ethical implications

The above results expose the gaps in ethical consideration or analysis in the patent approval process. It is becoming more and more important for stakeholders, such as designers, players, and regulators, to have discussions about moral design principles and the potential harm that manipulative strategies may cause [16, 17]. The academic literature emphasizes the necessity for greater awareness and literacy regarding these practices, particularly among vulnerable populations such as children [13, 14]. However, academic literature lacks adequate research on patents focusing on inappropriate or unfair content as part of it.

4 Conclusion

4.1 Summary of findings

Our research identified 34 unique instances of unfair practices in 10 patents (3 B2 and 7 A1 patents) through a systematic review of patent descriptions using OpenAI GPT-4-o-mini and Gemini 1.5 flash. The unfair patterns were validated based on three primary conditions: causing substantial injury to consumers, being unavoidable by consumers, and not being outweighed by countervailing benefits. The identified unfair practices created competitive imbalances, exploited players' 'fear of missing out,' exploited players with incentives for losses incurred, and influenced purchases or microtransactions. Matchmaking systems, limited-time events, exclusive power-ups, scarcity and urgency tactics, losses and incentives, exploiting player desires, and exploiting social dynamics were some of the identified dark patterns. The research concludes that these unfair patterns in video game patents are potentially unethical and manipulate players against their best interest.

4.2 Limitations of our research

Our research has 2 major limitations, namely, search limitations and detection and interpretation challenges. Firstly, our research focused on specific keywords and patents published after January 1, 2014, potentially missing relevant older patents or those using different terminology. This approach may have limited our understanding of evolving trends and unfair practices. Secondly, identifying unfair practices in patents presents several obstacles. Prompt-based approaches may struggle to capture nuances, while language models may not reliably detect all instances or may produce false positives/negatives. This limits the extent of coverage (number of patents) considered for review. Further, human review introduces subjectivity in interpreting unfair practices; this may also have an impact on our findings

4.3 Future research direction

We believe that there is a need for interdisciplinary research at the intersection of law, ethics, patent studies, and game studies. This could enable the development of more robust legal frameworks and ethical guidelines for the gaming industry. Additionally, specific research studies should explore the long-term implications for players, including potential addictive behaviors, psychological impacts, and economic consequences, arising from exposure to these unfair patterns

4.4 Recommendations

We propose two primary recommendations. (1) Encourage sufficient research on potentially illegal contents as part of patent invention and enable a systemic approach to address these in the patent approval process over a period. This can also include providing revised guidelines that address such concerns. (2) There is a need to have consistent self-regulation in avoiding potential exploitative patterns from digital games and stakeholders, including developers, shall consider industry-wide unified ethical guidelines to enable better games for players.

REFERENCES

- [1] Consumer Compliance Handbook. (n.d.). Federal Reserve. Retrieved from https://www.federalreserve.gov/publications/supervision_cch.htm.
- [2] Genshin Impact Game Developer Will Be Banned from Selling Lootboxes to Teens Under 16 Without Parental Consent, Pay a \$20 Million Fine to Settle FTC Charges. (n.d.). Federal Trade Commission. Retrieved from <https://www.ftc.gov/news-events/news/press-releases/2025/01/genshin-impact-game-developer-will-be-banned-selling-lootboxes-teens-under-16-without-parental>.

- [3] EPIC Games case: FTC Sends Refund Payments to Consumers Impacted by Epic Games' Unlawful Billing Practices. (n.d.). Federal Trade Commission. Retrieved from <https://www.ftc.gov/news-events/news/press-releases/2024/12/ftc-sends-refund-payments-consumers-impacted-epic-games-unlawful-billing-practices>.
- [4] King, J., Fitton, D., & Cassidy, B. (2023). Investigating Players' Perceptions of Deceptive Design Practices within a 3D Gameplay Context. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 7, Article 3611053. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3611053>.
- [5] King, D. L., & Delfabbro, P. H. (2019). Video Game Monetization (e.g., 'Loot Boxes'): A Blueprint for Practical Social Responsibility Measures. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 17, 166–179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-018-0009-3>.
- [6] Anderson, D., Stephenson, M., Togelius, J., Salge, C., Levine, J., & Renz, J. (2018). Deceptive Games. In *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Advances in Computer Entertainment Technology* (pp. 376–391). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-77538-8_26.
- [7] Bessant, C., Cook, L. A., Ong, L. L., Fox, A., Hoy, M. G., Gan, P., Nottingham, E., Pereira, B., & Steinberg, S. (2023). Exploring Parents' Knowledge of Dark Design and Its Impact on Children's Digital Well-Being. *AoIR Selected Papers of Internet Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5210/spir.v2023i0.13395>.
- [8] Dahlan, R. P., & Susanty, M. (2022). Finding Dark Patterns in Casual Mobile Games Using Heuristic Evaluation. *PETIR*, 15, 185–195. <https://doi.org/10.33322/petir.v15i2.1151>.
- [9] Van Nimwegen, C. (2023). Evil Design in the Dark Patterns Tunnel: Where We Came From and Where We Are (Heading) Now. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/122704017/evil_design_in_the_dark_patterns_tunnel_where_we_came_from_and_where_we_are_heading_now.
- [10] Phillips, C., Johnson, D., Klarkowski, M., White, M. J., & Hides, L. (2018). The Impact of Rewards and Trait Reward Responsiveness on Player Motivation. *Proceedings of the 2018 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play*, 393–404. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3242671.3242713>.
- [11] Rubin, V. L., & Camm, S. C. (2013). Deception in Video Games: Examining Varieties of Griefing. *Online Information Review*, 37, 369–387. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-10-2011-0181>.
- [12] Sarkar, A., Williams, M., Deterding, S., & Cooper, S. (2017). Engagement Effects of Player Rating System-Based Matchmaking for Level Ordering in Human Computation Games. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series, Part F130151*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3102071.3102093>.
- [13] Sousa, C., & Oliveira, A. (2023). The Dark Side of Fun: Understanding Dark Patterns and Literacy Needs in Early Childhood Mobile Gaming. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Games-Based Learning*, 599–610. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecgbl.17.1.1656>.
- [14] Tseng, F. C., & Teng, C. I. (2011). An Empirical Investigation into the Sources of Customer Dissatisfaction with Online Games. *International Journal of E-Business Research*, 7, 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jebr.2011100102>.
- [15] USPTO Kind Codes. (n.d.). United States Patent and Trademark Office. Retrieved from <https://www.uspto.gov/patents/search/authority-files/uspto-kind-codes>.
- [16] Obi, I., Gray, C. M., Chivukula, S. S., Duane, J.-N., Johns, J., Will, M., Li, Z., & Carlock, T. (2022). Let's Talk About Socio-Technical Angst: Tracing the History and Evolution of Dark Patterns on Twitter from 2010-2021.
- [17] Mathur, A., Kshirsagar, M., & Mayer, J. (2021). What Makes a Dark Pattern... Dark? *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445610>.
- [18] Petrovskaya, E., & Zendle, D. (2022). Predatory Monetisation? A Categorisation of Unfair, Misleading and Aggressive Monetisation Techniques in Digital Games from the Player Perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 181, 1065–1081. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04970-6>.
- [19] Tjostheim, I., Ayres-Pereira, V., Wales, C., Manna, A., & Egenfeldt-Nielsen, S. (2022). Dark Pattern: A Serious Game for Learning About the Dangers of Sharing Data. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Games-Based Learning*, 774–783. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecgbl.16.1.872>.
- [20] Zagal, J., Björk, S., & Lewis, C. (2013). Dark Patterns in the Design of Games. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/dark-patterns-in-the-design-of-games-zagal-bj%C3%B6rk/19a241378b06d868eb5f6b76027172c3aaca86f4>.